

ESA AO/1-9172/17/I-BG-BALTIC+

BALTIC+ Theme 3 Baltic+ SEAL (Sea Level)

Validation Report (VR)

From: Technische Universität München
Date: 08.12.2020
To: EUROPEAN SPACE AGENCY (ESA)
Subject: **ESA Contract: 4000126590/19/I/BG - BALTIC+ SEAL (Sea Level)**
Category: ESA Express Procurement Plus –EXPRO+
Deliverable: D3.2v2
Code: TUM_BSEAL_VR
Authors: Laura Rautiainen, Jani Särkkä, Laura Tuomi, Felix Müller, Marcello Passaro
Version: 2.2
Reviewed by: Marcello Passaro
DOI: 10.5270/esa.BalticSEAL.VRV2.2

Accepted by ESA	Signature	Date
J. Benveniste (ESA-ESRIN)		22/12/2020

LIST OF ACRONYMS

VR: Validation Report

ATBD: Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document

TG: Tide Gauge

DAC: Dynamic Atmosphere Correction

NAP: Normal Amsterdams Peil (Reference Frame)

RMSE: Root Mean Square Error

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1 INTRODUCTION

This document holds the Validation Report (VR) prepared by Baltic+ SEAL team, as part of the activities included in the WP3 of the Proposal. The documents present a summary of the statistics produced to validate different stages of the algorithm development. In particular, Section 2 summarises the results of the validation concerning the classification of the radar echoes in order to distinguish ice from open water; while Section 3 lists the main findings and statistics based on the comparison of the along-track raw high-rate dataset of sea level anomalies for each mission considered in this project against tide gauge data.

Compared to v1 of this document, Section 4 is added, which reports the validation statistics of the multi-mission gridded monthly dataset. Moreover, Section 3 is updated by considering the quality-flagged along-track data that will be delivered to ESA as final dataset.

2 VALIDATION OF THE CLASSIFICATION STRATEGY

The along-track open-water detection results of the unsupervised classification are compared with spatio-temporally matching optical and radar images, in order to evaluate the classification performance and reliability. Therefore, the classification results are overlain by image data, which are close in time (max. 1h) and show a good overlap to the altimetry overflights. The comparison of all included missions, except Envisat and SARAL/AltiKa, which were validated in (Müller, Dettmering, Bosch, & Seitz, 2017), is conducted in the Bay of Bothnia due to seasonal ice coverage and the development of narrow leads. The unsupervised classification algorithm follows for all missions the same strategy and processing tools, which are explained in (Müller, Dettmering, Bosch, & Seitz, 2017) and the Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document (ATBD) of Baltic+ SEAL.

Following section shows visual comparisons of the various altimetry missions underlining the good performance of the individual classifications. The comparisons are summarised in a table for each mission. Due to a better readability and general view not all comparisons are visualized in the Validation Report. Grey highlighted comparisons can be found in the Appendix to VR v1.

The reliability of comparison is dependent on the sea-ice drift. Therefore, the acquisition time gap (in minutes) is provided for each overlap. The algebraic sign describes the chronological order of the record. If it's positive the altimetry overflight was before the image acquisition and vice versa.

In case of optical images, near black areas correspond to water openings within the sea-ice. Reddish regions indicate land topography and bluish as well as greyish different sea-ice types. Analysing (side-looking) radar images, lead areas appear as very thin elongated black areas, due to a very specular behaviour of smooth and calm surfaces. Moreover, an enhanced surface roughness leads to a brighter, more greyish grey level. However, very thin ice surfaces, like Nila (i.e. smooth surface) ice, with a thickness up to 5cm lead to appear very dark. Furthermore, open ocean areas are mostly featured by high grey-scale values, due to stronger wave movements. Due to this ambiguities, radar images are not in every case the best option for validating classification results.

ESA European Remote Sensing satellite 2 (ERS-2) and ESA Environmental Satellite (Envisat)

The radar altimeter RA-1 is mounted on the ERS-2 satellite platform and shows similar behaviour with its successor ESA mission Envisat carrying an improved radar altimeter version, RA-2. The classification of RA-1 waveforms follow the strategy of Envisat waveform, which were quantitatively validated by using 16 SAR images of CSA mission Radarsat-2 and JAXA ALOS in (Müller, Dettmering, Bosch, & Seitz, 2017), showing an overall performance of about 71% true detection rate. The validation is based on 15000 Envisat observations in the Greenland Sea. Due to fixed, adverse revisit times of ERS-2 and potential comparison missions, the comparison suffers from a sparse availability of overlaps in the northern Baltic region. Only optical images from Landsat mission 5 and 7 are suited to give an impression of the good detection rates of the ERS-2 open-water classification. The comparisons are labelled by a caption code, which are summarized in following Table.

Table 1 Comparison pairs - ERS-2

Caption	Validation Mission	Date
ERS-2_C1	Landsat-7	2001-04-22
ERS-2_C2	Landsat-7	2001-04-22
ERS-2_C3	Landsat-7	2002-03-06
ERS-2_C4	Landsat-7	2003-04-17
ERS-2_C5	Landsat-5	1997-03-25
ERS-2_C6	Landsat-7	2000-04-08

Comparison: ERS-2_C1

Comparison: ERS-2_C2

Comparisons ERS-2_C1 and ERS-2_C2 show a very nice classification performance. The classification algorithm identifies smallest leads up to several meters and can detect ice returns originating from different sea-ice types (floes, Nila ice). At the top of ERS-2_C1 fast ice areas, producing ocean like returns, are reliable assigned to ice areas.

CNES/NASA Jason-1, Jason-2, Jason-3

Since the CNES/NASA missions Jason-1, Jason-2 and Jason-3 are characterized by very similar instrumental features and orbit characteristics, the classification of radar waveforms of all three missions is based by using Jason-2 radar echoes as a reference. Moreover, the extended mission parts (e.g. geodetic mission phases) are treated equally.

Table 2 Comparison pairs - Jason-1, Jason-2, Jason-3

Caption	Validation Mission	Date
J1_C1	Landsat-5	2006-04-28
J1_C2	Landsat-5	2011-02-28
J2_C3	Sentinel-1A	2015-01-16
J2_C4	Sentinel-1A	2015-01-20
J2_C5	Sentinel-1A	2015-01-23
J2_C6	Sentinel-1A	2015-02-04
J2_C7	Landsat-8	2016-04-14
J2_C8	Landsat-8	2016-04-14
J2_C9	Sentinel-1A	2015-03-19
J2_C10	Landsat-8	2016-04-21
J2_C11	Sentinel-1A	2015-03-19
J2_C12	Sentinel-1A	2015-03-28
J2_C13	Sentinel-1A	2015-03-30
J2_C14	Sentinel-1A	2016-01-06
J2_C15	Sentinel-1A	2016-01-13
J2_C16	Sentinel-1A	2016-01-23
J2_C17	Sentinel-1A	2016-03-08
J2_C18	Sentinel-1A	2016-03-12
J2_C19	Sentinel-1A	2016-03-22
J2_C20	Sentinel-1A	2016-03-29
J2_C21	Sentinel-1B	2017-01-06
J2_C22	Landsat-8	2017-04-08
J2_C23	Sentinel-1B	2017-02-27
J2_C24	Sentinel-1B	2017-03-09
J2_C25	Sentinel-1B	2017-04-17
J2_C26	Sentinel-1B	2017-04-24
J3_C27	Sentinel-1A	2016-03-08
J3_C28	Sentinel-2A	2018-03-23
J3_C29	Landsat-8	2016-04-14
J3_C30	Landsat-8	2016-04-14
J3_C31	Sentinel-1A	2016-03-22
J3_C32	Landsat-8	2016-04-21
J3_C33	Sentinel-1A	2016-03-29
J3_C34	Sentinel-2A	2018-03-30
J3_C35	Landsat-8	2017-03-30
J3_C36	Sentinel-2A	2019-03-22
J3_C37	Sentinel-2A	2019-03-22
J3_C38	Sentinel-2B	2018-03-08
J3_C39	Landsat-8	2017-04-17
J3_C40	Sentinel-2B	2018-03-15
J3_C41	Landsat-8	2018-03-19
J3_C42	Landsat-8	2019-03-26
J3_C43	Landsat-7	2018-03-27
J3_C44	Sentinel-2B	2019-03-07
J3_C45	Landsat-8	2018-04-02
J3_C46	Sentinel-1B	2017-03-11
J3_C47	Landsat-7	2019-03-07
J3_C48	Landsat-8	2019-03-22
J3_C49	Sentinel-1B	2017-04-26
J3_C50	Sentinel-1B	2017-04-29
J3_C51	Sentinel-1B	2018-02-13
J3_C52	Sentinel-1B	2018-02-17
J3_C53	Sentinel-1B	2018-02-27
J3_C54	Sentinel-1B	2018-03-02
J3_C55	Sentinel-1B	2018-03-04
J3_C56	Sentinel-1B	2018-04-07
J3_C57	Sentinel-1B	2018-04-21
J3_C58	Sentinel-1B	2018-04-26

Comparison: J2_C7

Comparison: J2_C19

Comparison: J3_C29

Comparison: J3_C31

Comparison: J3_C36

Comparison: J3_C40

The comparison for the CNES/NASA missions using one reference model, show for all three missions the same results. Comparison J2_C19 and J3_C31 as well as J2_C7 and J3_C29 are based on the same background radar/optical image. Jason-2 and Jason-3 are in tandem phase operation, just separated 2 minutes from each other. The number of water detections is nearly identical. However, some a few open water returns are registered by Jason-2. Explanations might be a changed situation due to drifting sea-ice or slight instrumental changes resulting in a differing waveform

characteristics between both missions. Comparisons J3_C36 and J3_C40 display different sea-ice situations, with a satisfying classification performance.

CNES/ISRO SARAL/AltiKa

The unsupervised classification of 40Hz SARAL/AltiKa observations was validated in the Greenland Sea following the descriptions of (Müller, Dettmering, Bosch, & Seitz, 2017). The validation is based on nearly 20000 altimetry observations and 19 radar images as comparison dataset and yields a consistency rate of about 77%. The classification strategy is directly transferable without any modifications to the Baltic Sea. Therefore, the same detection performance can be assumed and expected.

Copernicus/ESA Sentinel-3A/B

The unsupervised classification strategy is also adapted to Delay-Doppler waveforms of Copernicus ESA satellites Sentinel-3A/B. However, most of the comparison are referred to Sentinel-3A, due to the currently short mission time of Sentinel-3B with launch in April-2018.

Table 3 Comparison pairs Sentinel-3A/B

Caption	Validation Mission	Date
S3A_C1	Landsat-8	2017-03-16
S3A_C2	Sentinel-2A	2018-04-09
S3A_C3	Landsat-7	2017-03-31
S3A_C4	Landsat-7	2017-03-31
S3A_C5	Landsat-8	2017-04-08
S3A_C6	Landsat-8	2017-04-08
S3A_C7	Landsat-8	2018-02-22
S3A_C8	Landsat-8	2018-02-22
S3A_C9	Sentinel-2B	2018-04-17
S3A_C10	Sentinel-2B	2018-04-17
S3A_C11	Sentinel-2B	2018-04-17
S3A_C12	Sentinel-2B	2019-03-03
S3A_C13	Landsat-7	2019-03-30
S3A_C14	Sentinel-2B	2019-03-03
S3A_C15	Landsat-8	2019-04-07
S3A_C16	Landsat-7	2019-04-22
S3A_C17	Sentinel-2B	2019-03-03
S3A_C18	Sentinel-2B	2019-03-07
S3A_C19	Sentinel-2B	2019-03-30
S3B_C20	Landsat-7	2019-02-26
S3B_C21	Sentinel-2A	2019-03-25
S3B_C22	Landsat-7	2019-04-13
S3B_C23	Sentinel-2A	2019-04-17
S3B_C24	Sentinel-2A	2019-04-17
S3B_C25	Sentinel-2B	2019-04-09

Comparison: S3A_C7

Comparison: S3A_C9

Slight changes in the feature space are required for adapting the unsupervised classification approach to Delay-Doppler waveforms. In particular, in this case the feature space is obtained in the following way:

Sentinel-3A/B

- Waveform maximum - Computation without atmospheric attenuation
- Leading edge slope – obtained by subtracting the first bin position containing more than 12.5% of the power maximum from the bin position of the maximum power. The difference provides relative information about the width and steepness of the leading edge independent of the absolute position of the leading edge, i.e., the range.
- Waveform width – obtained by counting the numbers of bins below 2.5% of the maximum power

Cryosat-2

- Adaption of classification functions for a bin number of 256 bins
- Waveform maximum - Computation without atmospheric attenuation
- Leading edge slope – obtained by subtracting the first bin position containing more than 12.5% of the power maximum from the bin position of the maximum power. The difference provides relative information about the width and steepness of the leading edge independent of the absolute position of the leading edge, i.e., the range.
- Trailing edge slope – similar to leading edge slope, but number of bins counted from the last bin to first bin from the back exceeding 12.5% of the maximum waveform power
- Waveform width – obtained by counting the numbers of bins below 1% of the maximum power

In general, the classification results of Sentinel-3A/B are convincing. Sea-ice floes or rough sea-ice surfaces are detected and flagged (e.g. S3A-C9, S3B_C21). However, an unexpected behaviour of the absolute backscatter coefficients with respect to thin ice can be observed. Comparison S3A_C7 shows areas with a very thin refreezing sea-ice layer resulting in a water-ice mixture, which produces very strong backscatter coefficients. The values are even higher than the backscatter from leads, which leads to miss-classifications and additional water detections. Figure 2.1 shows an ice chart from 2018-02-22 indicating different ice-types. Nila-ice as well as new-ice regions are illustrated in light green up to yellow. Nearly all observations within these parts are assigned to water detections. Moreover, Delay-Doppler observations of Cryosat-2 are not affected in the same way, like returning radar echoes from Sentinel-3A/B. One explanation might be a changed handling of the incoming waveforms and backscatter treatment or the adjustment of the Automatic Gain Control in connection with the generation of Multi-Look waveforms of Sentinel-3A/B. Nevertheless, the nila-ice and new-ice layer are very thin (i.e. several centimetres) and radar echoes from these surface can be seen as reflected by the water level.

Figure 2.1 Cryosat-2 overflight with classification results and sea-ice chart from 2018-02-22, displaying different ice types. Nila-ice in light green; new-ice in yellow; fast-ice in black, hummocked ice in dark green and closed ice with leads in green (©FMI, (Berglund & Eriksson, 2015))

ESA Cryosat-2

The unsupervised classification approach is also applied to CryoSat-2 Delay-Doppler waveform data.

Table 4 Comparison pairs CryoSat-2

Caption	Validation Mission	Date
CS2_C1	Sentinel-1A	2016-03-16
CS2_C2	Sentinel-1A	2016-03-20
CS2_C3	Sentinel-1A	2016-04-10
CS2_C4	Sentinel-2A	2019-03-22
CS2_C5	Sentinel-1A	2016-04-10
CS2_C6	Sentinel-1B	2018-02-18
CS2_C7	Sentinel-1B	2018-02-20
CS2_C8	Sentinel-1B	2018-02-28
CS2_C9	Sentinel-1B	2018-03-02
CS2_C10	Sentinel-1B	2018-03-16
CS2_C11	Sentinel-1B	2018-03-19
CS2_C12	Sentinel-1B	2018-03-21
CS2_C13	Sentinel-1B	2018-03-28
CS2_C14	Sentinel-1B	2018-04-16

The Cryosat-2 classification results show very good performance, which is confirmed by Dettmering et al. 2018. The unsupervised classification, using 25 clusters, was independently validated by high-resolved optical images from NASA Operation Ice Bridge resulting in an overall classification accuracy of 97%, which can be directly transferred to the

Baltic Sea region. Very small leads are detected (CS2_7). However, roughed ice areas, characterized by small ice and snow-covered hummocks are tending to ocean-like radar shapes, which are falsely assigned to ocean conditions. The problem can be solved by introducing external sea-ice charts labelling hummocked ice areas to the process.

3 VALIDATION OF THE ALONG-TRACK DATASET

For a complete description of the collection and processing of the tide gauge (TG) data, the reader is referred to the Dataset Description report of this project (D2.1). The following sections and figures are to be considered as a resume of the full set of figures (over a hundred, consisting of all the TG-altimetry coupling for every along-track mission), which can be made available under request.

3.1 Methods

The TG and altimeter sea level measurements are not equivalent and hence both data sets were further processed before they were compared. The altimeter data sets are corrected for atmospheric pressure effect using Dynamic Atmosphere Correction (DAC). As applying the DAC to the TG data would further complicate the comparison, the altimetry data was decorrelated by adding the DAC back to the sea level height before the comparison, as done previously, for example, by Ruiz Etcheverry et al. (2015). The TG sea level data was also detrended. Detrending removes the effect of land uplift, prominent especially in the northern Baltic Sea, in the TG data.

In order to validate the new altimeter data sets, the nearest altimeter track points to TGs were calculated for each cycle 3-10 km away from the tide gauges and within 10 km from the coast, using the distance to coast parameter in the altimeter data set. Track points 0-3 km away from the coast are flagged as bad by the quality flag, since the 3-km limit is the typical limit of confidence that is assigned to ALES+ data according to previous studies (Passaro et al., 2018). As TGs are located on the coastlines, the performance of the altimeter data set was explored in the vicinity of the shoreline, allowing testing of the limits of the altimeter product in the complex Baltic archipelagos. The TG data has high temporal resolution (at least one hour) which allowed the interpolation of the EVRF2007 heights to the time of the altimeter overpass with one minute accuracy (similarly to Birol and Delebecque, 2014).

There is a clear difference in sea level reference frame as the altimeter sea level height is tied to the TOPEX ellipsoid, and TG sea level height data to Normaal Amsterdams Peil (NAP) reference frame. Hence the altimeter sea level was brought to the EVRF2007 level by setting the time-average from the altimeter data equal to the TG time-average for each TG and altimetry mission separately. This allowed for visual inspection of the time series variability but inhibits the comparison of means.

In the validation process for the initial dataset (VR v1), measured maximum and minimum values from the TG data were used to filter out bad altimeter data. This was a very rough way to gauge outliers from the data but provided a way to analyse the results without outliers. To improve the validation and for user purposes, a new quality flag was developed for the final dataset. As mentioned, the quality flag removes data within 3 km from the coast. It also removes erroneous fitting of LRM waveforms based on thresholds of the fitting error, all sea-ice waveforms and points where the difference between sea surface height and mean sea surface are greater than 2 m. For a detailed list of criteria for the quality flag, the reader is referred to the ATBD v2 (<http://doi.org/10.5270/esa.BalticSEAL.ATBDV2.1>). Sentinel-3A SAMOSA2 product does not have a quality flag and outliers were filtered by using only track points classified as water, excluding data within 3 km from the coast and removing SSH greater than 2 times the standard deviation. Nevertheless, we reckon that the parameter "mqe_ocean_20_ku", which corresponds to a mean quadratic error of the fitting of SAMOSA2 and is available in the official Sentinel-3 product, could have been used to derive a threshold that can be used for quality control.

The root mean square error (RMSE), Pearson correlation (r) and number (n) of along-track data points used in the comparison were computed for all TGs and altimetry missions. As the statistics would not be representative for $n < 20$, those results were left out of the validation. For Sentinel-3A, both ALES+ SAR and SAMOSA2 retrackerers were applied. To further investigate Sentinel-3A and compare the two retrackerers, results of all TG-retracker pairs were plotted in the same scatter plot. As the Sentinel-3B mission started only in 2018, there are very few points to analyse ($n < 20$). Hence, to see some results, a similar plot was made as for Sentinel-3A ALES+ SAR and SAMOSA2. Furthermore, the geodetic phase of Jason-1 mission and the interleaved phase of Jason-2 mission were left out, as there were only three TGs with $n > 20$.

3.2. Validation results

We have chosen eight TGs (Figure 3.1) with large number of data points so that the statistics is based on larger dataset and different altimetry missions can be compared for the same TGs. Only some TGs are situated within 3-10 km distance from altimeter tracks, which limits the spatial coverage of validation points. The selected TGs are Bagenkop, Ballen, Daugavgriva, Kalix, Kaskinen, Kemi, Mäntyluoto (close to Pori, Finland) and Rodvig. The best validation results are obtained from SARAL/AltiKa mission, where RMSE is under 12 cm and r is over 0.85 for seven tide gauges. Overall, Kemi (eight missions) has best results (RMSE under 10 cm and r over 0.9 excepting Cryosat).

In order to further interpret the results, some considerations are necessary on the locations of the tide gauges. Kalix and Kemi are representative of conditions in which sea ice plays a major role during winter, i.e. the Bothnian Bay. Therefore, the validation of along-track data is mostly restricted to the sea-ice-free season. Ballen, Rodvig and

Bagenkop are located in the Danish Straits, which besides being an important area for water exchange between the Baltic and the North Sea, it is extremely challenging for coastal altimetry due to the presence of multiple land-ocean transitions and islands. Kaskinen and Mäntyluoto, in the eastern coast of the Gulf of Bothnia, are also located in bays where several islets are present, while Daugavgriva is located at the estuary of the river Daugava in the Gulf of Riga.

Scatter plots and time series for five different tide gauges and missions are shown. In the scatter plots, the fitted linear curve is shown with correlation and the number of points. The scatter plot of Cryosat-2 at Kemi (Fig.3.2) has $r = 0.87$ and the time series plot (Fig.3.3) shows that the extremes are well captured in the altimeter data 2010-2019. For Jason-1, there are 382 data points at Mäntyluoto (Fig.3.4, $r=0.94$) and the time series 2002-2009 (Fig.3.5) exhibits very good correspondence between altimeter and TG data. At Kalix, there are 163 data points in Jason-2 data with $r = 0.97$ (Fig. 3.6). The time series 2008-2016 (Fig.3.7) shows that the extremes are well approximated in the altimeter data. Daugavgriva is situated at coast of the Gulf of Riga. Correlation in the scatter plot of SARAL/AltiKa mission is high (Fig.3.8, $r=0.96$) and altimeter and TG time series are close to each other (Fig.3.9). The differences in Sentinel-3A data between ALES+ SAR and SAMOSA2 retracers are very small. When outliers are excluded from the data, the numbers of data points differ between retracers for some TGs. In Bagenkop, $n < 20$ for SAMOSA2, and only statistics for ALES+ SAR is shown in Table 13. This shows that in this location ALES+ SAR is able to retrack more valid points than SAMOSA2, which is promising given that the area is affected by sea ice in the winter season. Even if the Sentinel-3A (ALES+ SAR) data has only few points at Rodvig ($n=30$), the correlation is high (Fig.3.10, $r=0.94$) and altimeter and TG time series are quite similar (Fig.3.11). Tables 5-13 show the statistical validation results for these TGs and 9 missions.

Scatter plots of the all TG-Sentinel-3A pairs can be seen in Figure 3.12 for ALES+ SAR retracker and Figure 3.13 for SAMOSA2 retracker. ALES+ SAR performed well ($r=0.93$) and significantly better than SAMOSA2 ($r=0.59$). The outperformance of ALES+ SAR is due to the use of the quality flag that is not available for SAMOSA2 as some outliers fall within the 2 times standard deviation marginal.

We report that a further activity in the project has validated results from ALES+ SAR against results from SAMOSA+ (a dedicated retracker for coastal and sea ice areas which is available through ESA GPOD service) using the TG data from Onsala and 33 cycles for 2 tracks of Sentinel3a. The study concluded that, ALES+ SAR is able to retrieve more valid points than SAMOSA+, while maintaining the same level of correlation in the last 5 km from the coast. All results are available from Passaro et al. 2020.

The following conclusions can be drawn by this analysis:

- 1) A careful outliers analysis is unavoidable if coastal altimetry data have to be applied for sea level analysis at high rate. The results of this validation show that the compromise found within Baltic+ SEAL provides a reliable along-track product for the users in the vast majority of the locations.
- 2) The ALES+ SAR dataset shows performances that are at least comparable to SAMOSA2 and allows a larger number of valid points to be retrieved in zones affected by seasonal sea ice. This is encouraging and allows to apply the ALES+ SAR retracking with confidence for Cryosat-2 data as well. Nevertheless this comparison cannot be considered as a fully fair comparison between the two retracers, since the quality flag of ALES+ SAR is more advanced than the one used in SAMOSA2. It has to be taken in consideration, nevertheless, that the SAMOSA2 retrievals are the ones offered to the users by the official data providers. We have also shown that in several locations, particularly in the sea-ice region, ALES+ SAR provides more retrieval AND higher performances, which is expected since SAMOSA2 is not a product adapted for these conditions.
- 3) Among the Ku-Band LRM missions, Envisat performs best. This was already noticed for ALES data and it is likely due to the better performances of the on-board tracker compared to the Jason series, which allows more valid waveforms to be retrieved in the transitions between land and ocean. Moreover Envisat had a smaller footprint than the Jason satellites, due to the different orbit altitude.
- 4) ERS-2 can be successfully retracked in the coastal zone, despite the fact that its waveforms are noisier, because they are formed by averaging half of the individual echoes used for the same procedure in the other LRM altimeters. This justifies the consideration of the ERS-2 mission for the multi-mission gridded dataset in output of this project and allows to analyse the sea level in the Baltic area starting from May 1995
- 5) We noted in the VR v1 that Jason-3 had worse performances than Jason-2 and Jason-1. Using the quality flag, these performances are now equivalent. One possibility to explain this behaviour is that Jason-3 benefits from a better on-board tracking system that allows more waveforms to be retrieved in the proximity of land. These waveforms nevertheless might be in some cases highly corrupted and therefore not correctly retracked.
- 6) We are aware that flagging data closer than 3 km from the coast causes the loss of a significant amount of useful retrievals. This is true not only for SAR waveforms, but also for LRM altimeters, as demonstrated by recent studies (Benveniste et al., 2020). The outlier analysis at distances closer than 3 km from the coast requires an effort that goes beyond the possibilities within this project. We recommend future studies to investigate a dedicated quality flag for coastal proximities, since all retrievals are provided in the product offered to the users (data flagged as bad are not removed from the along-track product).

Figure 3.1. The selected tide gauges.

Table 5. Cryosat -2 SAR mode

Tide gauge	RMSE	r	n
Bagenkop	0.13	0.85	58
Ballen	0.12	0.9	42
Daugavgriva	0.13	0.85	28
Kaskinen	0.09	0.95	33
Kemi	0.16	0.87	34
Mantyluoto	0.07	0.96	24
Rodvig	0.14	0.86	60

Table 6. Envisat

Tide gauge	RMSE	r	n
Bagenkop	0.08	0.89	29
Ballen	0.09	0.9	62
Daugavgriva	0.08	0.91	40
Kaskinen	0.08	0.93	73
Kemi	0.08	0.97	49
Mantyluoto	0.08	0.94	109
Rodvig	0.07	0.91	59

Table 7. ERS-2

Tide gauge	RMSE	r	n
Ballen	0.08	0.94	72
Kaskinen	0.11	0.88	64
Kemi	0.08	0.95	40
Mantyluoto	0.12	0.83	102
Rodvig	0.1	0.92	68

Table 8. Jason-1

Tide gauge	RMSE	r	n
Ballen	0.1	0.89	212
Daugavgriva	0.1	0.92	87
Kalix-Storon	0.07	0.97	90
Kaskinen	0.08	0.93	192
Kemi	0.08	0.92	26
Mantyluoto	0.08	0.94	382

Table 9. Jason-1_EM

Station	RMSE	r	n
Ballen	0.13	0.87	65
Kalix-Storon	0.1	0.93	40
Kemi	0.08	0.97	53

Table 10. Jason-2

Tide gauge	RMSE	r	n
Bagenkop	0.07	0.93	30
Ballen	0.13	0.8	269
Daugavgriva	0.08	0.93	177
Kalix-Storon	0.07	0.97	163
Kaskinen	0.08	0.93	229

Kemi	0.09	0.95	98
Mantyluoto	0.08	0.93	459

Table 11. Jason-3

Tide gauge	RMSE	r	n
Bagenkop	0.07	0.9	36
Ballen	0.1	0.88	109
Daugavgriva	0.14	0.85	42
Kalix-Storon	0.09	0.95	68
Kaskinen	0.07	0.94	97
Kemi	0.08	0.95	39
Mantyluoto	0.09	0.91	190

Table 12. SARAL/AltiKa

Tide gauge	RMSE	r	n
Bagenkop	0.09	0.88	27
Ballen	0.08	0.93	29
Daugavgriva	0.06	0.96	26
Kaskinen	0.06	0.95	30
Kemi	0.06	0.98	20
Mantyluoto	0.08	0.95	34
Rodvig	0.11	0.85	22

Table 13. Sentinel-3A

Station	RMSE	r	n	SAMOSA2	ALES+ SAR
Bagenkop	0.04	0.97	28		x
Rodvig	0.06	0.96	31	x	
Rodvig	0.07	0.94	30		x

Figure 3.2. Scatter plot Kemi Cryosat-2

Figure 3.3. Time series Kemi Cryosat-2

Figure 3.4. Scatter plot Mäntyluoto Jason-1

Figure 3.5. Time series Mäntyluoto Jason-1

Figure 3.6. Scatter plot Kalix Jason-2

Figure 3.7. Time series Kalix Jason-2

Figure 3.8. Scatter plot Daugavgriva SARAL/AltiKa

Figure 3.9. Time series Daugavgriva SARAL/AltiKa

Figure 3.10. Scatter plot Rodvig Sentinel-3A ALES+ SAR

Figure 3.11. Time series Rodvig Sentinel-3A ALES+ SAR

Figure 3.12. Scatter plot of Sentinel-3A ALES+ SAR

Figure 3.13. Scatter plot of Sentinel-3A SAMOSA2

Figure 3.14. Scatter plot of Sentinel-3B

4 VALIDATION OF THE GRIDDED DATASET

4.1 METHODS

In order to validate the gridded dataset, the grid points within 20 km from every TG were located. As the gridded dataset has a frequency of a month, the TG data were monthly averaged. Only TG data with the quality flag of 1 (Good) or 8 (Interpolated) were used for the averaging and 20 days worth of data were needed to calculate the mean for the month.

TGs measure relative sea level and altimeters measure absolute sea level, hence the effect of land uplift was removed from the TG data using the Glacial Isostatic Adjustment (GIA) model NKG2016LU by Vestol *et al.* (2019). NKG2016LU is the latest GIA model for the Baltic Sea. The closest absolute land uplift values were located for each TG and used for trend removal. The importance of this measure can be seen in Figures 4.1 and 4.2.

Figure 4.1. Time series from Vaasa with and without the effect of land uplift. Vaasa is located relatively near the point of maximum land uplift at the Baltic Sea and the effect on sea level becomes visibly significant in the almost 30 year long time series.

Figure 4.2. Time series from Ballen with and without the effect of land uplift. Ballen is located at the Belt Sea where the effect of land uplift is smaller compared to Vaasa but still significant.

Erroneous grid data was filtered out before the comparison by using the quality flag of the grid product and only data within 20 km from TGs were used. An explanation of the criteria used to assign the quality flag on each monthly grid point is found in the Algorithm Theoretical Baseline Document Version 2.1 (<http://doi.org/10.5270/esa.BalticSEAL.ATBDV2.1>).

Futhermore, there is a clear difference in sea level reference frame as the altimeter sea level height is tied to the TOPEX ellipsoid, and TG sea level height data to Normaal Amsterdams Peil (NAP) reference frame. Hence the altimeter sea level was brought to the EVRF2007 level by setting the time-average from the grid data equal to the TG time-average

for each TG and grid time series separately. This allowed for visual inspection of the time series variability but inhibits the comparison of means.

The root mean square error (RMSE), Pearson correlation (r) and number (n) of data points used in the comparison were computed for all TG-grid pair time series. As the statistics would not be representative for $n < 20$, those results were left out of the validation. The results were divided into categories by their basin and scatter plots were made for each BS basin. The effects of using the quality flag and averaging of grid points were also examined.

4.2 RESULTS

106 TG-grid pairs were formed after pre-processing. For 80 pairs, the RMSE was 9 cm or less and for 99 pairs RMSE was 12 cm or less. Statistically significant correlation (r) was at its highest 0.96 and at its lowest 0.3 (Ballen) with $r > 0.9$ for 18 pairs, $r > 0.8$ for 54 pairs, $r > 0.7$ for 74 pairs and $r > 0.6$ for 86 pairs. The same eight TGs, Bagenkop, Ballen, Daugavgriva, Kalix, Kaskinen, Kemi, Mäntyluoto (close to Pori, Finland) and Rodvig, were selected for closer examination as in the along-track product validation (Table 14). Out of the eight TG-grid pairs Mäntyluoto performed the best with RMSE of 10 cm and r of 0.85 while for Ballen the results were less successful with RMSE of 14 cm and r of 0.3 (Table 14). Furthermore, all of the individual TG-grid pair results can be examined in Figures 4.3 and 4.4.

All in all, the grid product performed well, 13732 data point pairs were used for the validation with r of 0.84 (Figure 4.5). To further inspect the results, the TG-grid pairs were divided into groups by basin and further grouped by season (Figures 4.6-4.15): Winter (December, January, February; DJF in the figures), Spring (March, April, May; MAM in the figures), Summer (June, July, August, JJA in the figures), Autumn (September, October, November; SON in the figures)

Moreover, the grid product performed well across the ten basins, $r > 0.9$ for 2 basins, $r > 0.8$ for 6 basins, $r > 0.7$ for 8 basins, 0.69 for the Bothnian Sea and 0.61 for the Great Belt (Figures 4.6-4.15). The Great Belt is a very important area for water exchange between the Baltic and the North Sea but is an exceptionally difficult region for altimeter sea level detection due to many land-ocean transitions and islands. When acknowledging the limitations, correlation of 0.61 can be considered a reasonable result for a gridded product in this fragmented and dynamic region. Furthermore, the Åland and Archipelago Seas (Figure 4.8.), another region fragmented by many islands, performs very well with r of 0.87 and RMSE of 8 cm. Out of the basins, the Bornholm Basin performs the best with r of 0.92 and RMSE of 5 cm (Figure 4.9.).

In the Gulf of Bothnia season has a strong effect on the results as almost all of the visual outliers belong to winter-spring months when sea ice is present in the region (Figures 4.6 and 4.7). From the results it appears that the retrieval of sea surface height in the northern Baltic Sea is hindered due to presence of sea ice. In order to investigate the issue, therefore, grids within 20 km from the TG were used (instead of only looking for the closest grid point). This significantly improves results especially in the Gulf of Bothnia when compared to only using the closest grid (Figure 4.16). Sea ice is a dynamic surface that complicates synoptic sea surface height measurements as the measurements are limited to periodic narrow openings in the ice cover (leads). In the presence of sea ice, the altimeter sea surface height is determined from very few leads available which do not always fall within the closest grid. Hence using the averaged sea surface height from several adjacent grids is preferable as averaging does not remarkably impair results in other regions (Figure 4.16).

Using the quality flag improved correlation results at few TGs located on the Finnish coast but the correlation also decreased at certain TGs (Figure 4.17). However when trends for the whole domain were estimated, the quality flag significantly improved the results (Figure 4.18). Without quality flag RMSE is 1.41 and with quality flag 0.896. The use of quality flag therefore decreases the RMSE by 0.514. Thus using the quality flag produces more reliable trend estimations. The sea level trends are analyzed in full detail in the Impact Assessment Report. Investigating the reasons why the quality control improves trend retrieval but decreases correlation is a both interesting and important topic that should be further investigated in future studies.

The following conclusions can be drawn by this analysis:

- 1) The gridding process in coastal and sea-ice covered areas is extremely challenging, since it requires interpolations to cover areas in which no along-track data are present, given the very variable spatial coverage of the domain depending on the years considered.
- 2) Given that this is the first effort ever to build a dedicated gridded product in coastal and sea ice environments, the results obtained are satisfactory. Critical areas where the correlation of the gridding product are located in particular in the Danish Straits
- 3) The closest grid points located in seasonally sea-ice covered regions show a good correlation, but a reduced number of points. This is understandable, since the possibility to obtain a monthly estimation of the sea level during winter months depends on the amount of leads that can be retracked. In the figures presented, we have shown how several coastal points have good sea level estimations even during the months of sea-ice coverage.

Table 14. Root mean square error (RMSE), Pearson correlation (r) and number of points (n) for selected TG-grid pairs

TG	RMSE	r	n
Bagenkop	0.09	0.49	130
Ballen	0.14	0.3	228
Daugavgriva	0.1	0.84	124
Kalix-Storon	0.16	0.69	141
Kaskinen	0.11	0.82	282
Kemi	0.11	0.83	186
Mantyluoto	0.1	0.85	282
Rodvig	0.07	0.78	251

Figure 4.3. Correlation (% left) and RMSE (centimetres right) between the TG sea level and the nearest altimeter sea level grid product classified as good data.

Figure 4.4. Close up of the Belt Sea region from Figure 4.3. Correlation (%), left) and RMSE (centimetres, right) between the TG sea level and the nearest altimeter sea level grid product grid classified as good data.

Figure 4.5. Scatter plot of the TG-grid pair results.

Figure 4.6. Scatter plot of TG-grid pair results for the Bothnian Bay with different seasons in different colours indicated in the legend.

Figure 4.7. Scatter plot of TG-grid pair results for the Bothnian Sea with different seasons in different colours indicated in the legend.

Figure 4.8. Scatter plot of TG-grid pair results for the Åland and Archipelago Seas with different seasons in different colours indicated in the legend.

Figure 4.9. Scatter plot of TG-grid pair results for the Bornholm Basin with different seasons in different colours indicated in the legend.

Figure 4.10. Scatter plot of TG-grid pair results for the Kattegat Basin with different seasons in different colours indicated in the legend.

Figure 4.11. Scatter plot of TG-grid pair results for the Gulf of Riga with different seasons in different colours indicated in the legend.

Figure 4.12. Scatter plot of TG-grid pair results for the Gulf of Finland with different seasons in different colours indicated in the legend.

Figure 4.13. Scatter plot of TG-grid pair results for the Western Gotland Basin with different seasons in different colours indicated in the legend.

Figure 4.14. Scatter plot of TG-grid pair results for the Great Belt with different seasons in different colours indicated in the legend.

Figure 4.15. Scatter plot of TG-grid pair results for the Arkona Basin with different seasons in different colours indicated in the legend.

Figure 4.16. Comparing the effect of using the closest grid versus the grids within 20 km from the TGs for the validation.

Figure 4.17. Comparing the effect using the product quality flag for the validation.

Figure 4.18. Comparing the effect using the product quality flag for the trend estimation.

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